

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) APPLICATIONS IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES AND RESEARCH DATABASES

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1.1 Background to the Study

1.1.1 Global Perspectives

Academic libraries research databases play an important role in research and teaching activities around the world. They serve as learning and knowledge intermediaries, providing critical services to researchers, teachers, and students. People have historically offered these services, including as categorisation and classification, circulation, and reference. Libraries have long been at the forefront of promoting access to information and knowledge.

Libraries are adapting to new technology in the digital era in order to better serve their users. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in libraries is one of the most significant technological breakthroughs that can be implemented. The use of AI in libraries can improve services and provide clients with credible information, fostering growth and development in this information age. One of the advantages of AI for library operations is its ability to do tasks more efficiently (Divayana et al. 2015). Libraries that employ artificial intelligence can finish jobs much faster than people. Apparently, in this new age, AI and librarians are assisting each other to provide people with the finest possible service.

According to Kristin (2016), the way people acquire information is continually evolving, and academic libraries can adjust their emphasis and attention using a variety of AI applications. AI is currently providing a very useful means of using this information and producing superior results because academic libraries are focusing on using AI to increase access to materials. Artificial intelligence and advanced computer technology will have a significant impact on the nature of libraries in the future, with quality differences that may differ from what our current research predicts.

According to a study conducted by Tella (2020), academic libraries in developed countries have embraced and practically integrated AI technologies into all aspects of their operations,

whereas academic libraries in underdeveloped countries are still getting started. According to Grant and Camp (2018), many university libraries, particularly those in industrialised nations, have integrated AI into their operations for things like circulation and reference services. The integration and eventual acceptance of AI may have a favourable impact on library services, which are now being investigated and discussed (Massis, 2018).

1.1.2 African Perspectives

Academic libraries in Africa, like other industries, have seen significant modifications over the years, moving from manual operations to the use of cutting-edge technologies to improve library utilisation and ease service access. Notable improvements include the shift from traditional card catalogues to Online Public Access catalogues (OPAC), which simplifies information retrieval and eliminates the need for lengthy manual searches (Eserada 2019). Furthermore, the accessibility of library services in most African countries has greatly improved, allowing for remote subject support without physical presence (Adetayo 2023). These technological advancements have been critical in promoting increased library utilisation and research databases, which is especially relevant in the context of the fourth and fifth industrial revolutions (Oke and Fernandes, 2020).

Despite academic libraries' proactive use of AI to redefine service paradigms, there is still an evident gap in the total deployment of AI in the majority of African academic libraries (Alhajri 2021). While AI is being used to use big data and data analytics for operational and service-oriented goals, closing the implementation gap is critical to fully utilising these technical developments (Cox 2022). Recognising the importance of incorporating cutting-edge technologies such as AI into academic libraries in Africa, scholars have highlighted its potential to improve service accessibility, both on-site and online, as well as operational efficiency, resulting in increased engagement among staff and patrons (Ogar and Dushu 2018). Despite the acknowledged requirement and potential benefits, a gap in the application of AI in libraries in Africa academic libraries exists, necessitating immediate action to promote wider adoption (Wheatley and Hervieux 2019).

1.1.3 Zambia Perspectives

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly being integrated into Zambian academic libraries and research databases, with the goal of improving service delivery and operational efficiency. A research conducted by Subaveerapandiyan (2022) on Zambian librarians demonstrated a strong comprehension of AI foundations and a positive attitude towards its potential benefits in library services. However, issues such as the need for increased AI competence, reluctance to change, and budgetary limits were found.

According to Obeka (2024), in the field of research databases, AI applications are being investigated to improve information retrieval and management. For example, AI-powered systems can automate categorising and indexing duties, increasing the efficiency of research procedures. These developments enable libraries to provide more personalised learning experiences while also streamlining administrative duties. Despite these advances, the use of AI in Zambian academic libraries and research databases is still in its infancy. Addressing the mentioned difficulties would need ongoing efforts, such as investing in AI literacy training for

librarians and procuring appropriate financing. By overcoming these obstacles, Zambian academic institutions will be able to fully realise the potential of artificial intelligence to transform their library services and research capacity.

A study done by Kadeyo et al., (2025), on the navigating the future of academic library services and barriers to adopting 4IR technologies in academic libraries in Zambia revealed that Libraries, as critical institutions for knowledge transmission and access, have not been spared from the disruptive effects of the Artificial intelligence. Kadeyo et al (2025), postulates that library services are the procedures and operations involved in maintaining, developing and supporting library collections behind the scenes, such as acquisition, cataloguing, classification, interlibrary loan, document delivery, and serial systems as well as the shift toward the digitisation of library resources and services. As digital technologies have advanced, libraries have progressively turned to providing electronic resources such as e-books, online journals, and digital archives (Kadeyo et al., 2025). This transformation not only increases the accessibility of library materials but also necessitates new skills for librarians to efficiently manage digital collections as necessity in order to preserve the integrity.

The effect of the 4IR on academic library services is evident in several ways. Initially, there has been a shift toward digital collections and resources, with libraries progressively adopting digital platforms for organising, archiving and providing access to a diverse range of electronic resources such as e-books, ejournals, and online databases (Kadeyo et al., 2025). Furthermore, the use of automation technology has improved library operations by increasing efficiency in tasks such as inventory management and resource retrieval.

A study done by Kadeyo et al., (2025) on the 4IR in Academic Libraries: An Exploratory Study of Lusaka Province, Zambia revealed that AI holds immense potential for revolutionising library services. Libraries are leveraging artificial intelligence technologies such as powilld chatbots for virtual reference services, enhancing user interactions, and providing real-time assistance. Moreover, AI algorithms are employed for data mining and analysis, enabling libraries to extract valuable insights from vast collections and optimise resource allocation Kadeyo et al., (2025). In this context, Kadeyo et al (2025), conducted a study on the integration of artificial intelligence in libraries, and their study revealed that libraries can integrate robotics with other artificial intelligence technologies like a drone being controlled by a robot that can make sure that the libraries are always under surveillance, by just placing robots in various sections of the library as a user aid and guide.

Kadeyo et al (2025), further stated that the 4IR represents a complicated, dialectical, and exciting opportunity for higher education that can reshape society for the better. However, they warn that AI may shift the workplace from task-based to human-centred features. They argue that this may lessen the gap between the humanities and social sciences, as well as science and technology, resulting in a greater demand for interdisciplinary teaching, research, and innovation. The new environment is expected to include virtual classrooms and laboratories, virtual libraries and virtual teachers. That is why Kadeyo et al (2025), after looking at the application of artificial intelligence (AI) and chatbots in libraries have concluded that these technologies can help libraries provide personalised services to students and researchers,

enhance efficiency and minimise staff workload, making them very beneficial to libraries in providing library and information services to users.

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